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SPATIAL STRUCTURE OF GARDEN AND PARK LANDSCAPES OF CENTRAL EUROPE

Kravtsova I.

Uman National University of Horticulture

PhD in Geography, associated professor

Abstract

One of the important peculiarities of landscapes of different genesis and levels of organization is structurality. The structure of the landscape determines its physiognomic organization, shape, spatial and structural features. Garden and park landscapes are examples of constructive territory planning, cultural or «soft» use of natural conditions and resources, organization of supplementary interaction between man and nature. The spatial structure of the research objects is determined by the set of elementary landscape complexes at the local level of organization. The physiognomy – by the geological and geomorphological structure, vegetation, small architectural forms and palace, park complexes. Configuration – by the shape and dimensions of the garden and park landscape and the direction of the river valley.

Keywords: rational nature use, constructive geography, anthropogenic landscape science, Central Europe, structure, garden and park landscape.

Definition of the problem. One of the important properties of landscapes of different genesis and levels of organization is structurality. The landscape should be understood as a combination in a certain order and sequence of geographical components and elements connected to each other by horizontal and vertical flows of matter and energy. The structure of the landscape determines its physiognomic organization, shape, spatial and structural features. At the same time, the structure is determined by the space that this landscape occupies. Among the numerous man-made landscapes, garden and park landscapes are special. These landscape complexes are harbingers of the noosphere; an example of rational interaction between man and nature. Today, it is worth paying attention to the organization of garden and park landscapes, which were established in the XVII–XVIII centuries. These anthropogenic landscape complexes are examples of constructive territory planning that performs both spiritual and utilitarian functions; the so-called cultural or «soft» use of natural conditions and resources, the organization of supplementary interaction between man and nature. Therefore, the study of the spatial structure of garden and park landscapes of Central Europe is the actual scientific problem.

The analysis of recent researches and publications and the separation of unsolved aspects of the problem. The question of the structure of the landscape is revealed in the works of Ukrainian and foreign scientists. In particular, V.M. Volovik (2007) notes that structurality is an important property of the landscape, which results from the systematic nature of the landscape. The author claims that there is no structure without a system. In the general theory of systems, a structure is a set of relations of a certain type between elements. In practical applications of systems theory, a structure is a set of elements and the relationships between them. Also V.M. Volovik emphasizes that the structure can also be understood as a configuration of the landscape. According to the author, structurality in the theoretical-systemic sense is «... it is the property of the system to have internal connections between its

components, and in the expanded sense – the existence of its distinct parts connected to each other in the system». M.D. Grodzynskii (2005) reveals the issue of types of spatial configurations of the landscape, distinguishing between natural and socio-cultural configurations of the landscape. O.V. Golubtsov (2018) characterizes the image of the landscape, noting that it is the appearance of the object. The author writes: «the image of a landscape is not only a «picture» that appears in a person's imagination, but also impressions, emotional experiences, certain values and meanings that a person associates with the landscape». The criteria for assessing the image of the landscape are the diversity, originality and beauty of the landscape, which are determined by the components (natural components and elements; bodies of natural and anthropogenic origin). That is, actually, the structure of the landscape, which will indicate the uniqueness and beauty of the landscape complex. A.A. Klish, N.V. Maksymenko (2020) investigate the positional and dynamic territorial structure of the urban landscape. The authors determined and established the territorial configuration of different types of landscape strips based on the classical scheme of typology of landscape places according to the water-geochemical regime proposed by B. Polynov and supplemented by M. Glazovska; cartographic models of the positional and dynamic structure of Kharkiv landscapes were developed. The detected types of regimes and the nature of the spatial arrangement of the corresponding landscape strips are described in detail.

In the works of the foreign researchers more attention pay to the issue of landscape structure as an object of economic use (Zavadil T., Jancak V., 2021), territory planning and harmonization of the modern urban environment (Krutskikh N., 2021). They study the physiognomy of the landscape as a component of the scientific approach to the assessment and identification of the landscape complex, the theoretical basis of the physiognomy structure of landscapes, the theory of landscape interiors (Chmielewski T.J., Butler A., Chmielewski S., 2018). Assess the landscape

diversity of individual territories using various landscape metrics, including landscape structure and land use types (Venturi, M., Piras, F., Corrieri, F., Fiore, B., Santoro, A., Agnoletti, M., 2021). Analyze the role of spatial structure in the general image of landscape identity; cognitive aspects that a person perceives as a landscape identity through the general spatial structure, abstraction, smoothing of details and giving symbolic meaning; generalize the spatial structures of different landscapes, their diversity in both rural and urban environments, classifying them into types and subtypes; develop various spatial models and determine the role of spatial structure in understanding landscape identity and recommendations for the inclusion and preservation of important spatial structures and elements in the process of spatial planning (Nitavska N., 2020). They study the fragmentation and structural changes of landscapes caused by spatial ecological and social processes; spatio-temporal variations of the landscape model and structure of anthropogenically transformed territories based on the data of remote sensing of the Earth (Abbas Z., Zhu Z.Y., Zhao YL., 2022); spatial structure of landscapes in order to optimize territorial spatial planning, protection and management of landscapes (Pan YL., Wu YN., Xu X., Zhang B., Li WF., 2022; Festus OO., Ji W., Zubair O.A., 2020).

From the point of view of modern anthropogenic landscape science, Central Europe is the unique natural-ethno-cultural entity. The peculiarities of the natural conditions of this territory, the history of settlement and anthropogenic transformation – all this is reflected in the physiognomy of various classes of man-made landscapes of the study area. Central Europe as a natural-geographical region includes the central parts of Europe, which are distinguished by their geological and geomorphological structure and occupy an intermediate hypsometric position between the highlands of Western and Southern Europe, the mid-mountains of the North and the lowlands of Eastern Europe, clearly limited by the «loess deposits» extension [4, 6].

Garden and park landscapes are the group of man-made landscapes that are formed as a result of human economic activity aimed at satisfying material and spiritual needs; in which natural components (rocks, water, air, soil, vegetation, animal world, solar radiation) in combination with small architectural forms and structures, road and linear network form a harmonious, supplementary landscape system. These anthropogenic landscape complexes are saturated with various cultural artifacts, have a strong associative, historical aspect and, in our opinion, are the so-called landscape cultural identifiers of the respective regions. At the same time, this group of man-made landscapes should be considered as the one that carries information about the usual and unique features of the natural conditions of the region.

The purpose of the article to investigate the spatial structure of garden and park landscapes of Central Europe.

The feeding of the main material. The study of the spatial structure of garden and park landscapes of

Central Europe is based on the following approaches: chorological (geographical elements and components that form garden and park landscapes have an appropriate location on the physical surface of Central Europe, are characterized by spatial outlines and dimensions), systemic (we understand that the model territory is a complex geographical object formed by a set of interconnected components and elements of natural and anthropogenic genesis), historical (study of the dynamics of historical changes in the spatial contours and dimensions of garden and park landscapes in Central Europe). These approaches determine the corresponding principles of scientific research (chorological, systematic, historical), as well as the principle of natural-anthropogenic coexistence, which was revealed in the works of G.I. Denysyk (2012). The author notes that «... it is not enough to know only man-made landscapes. It is mandatory to study the man-made landscape as one of the components of the interacting paragenetic system» [5]. Man-made landscapes are formed and function in specific natural conditions and in close relationship with existing landscapes. Therefore, when studying them, it is important to take into account both the natural and socio-economic conditions of the region.

With the aim to investigate the spatial structure of garden and park landscapes of Central Europe, both general scientific and specific scientific research methods were used. On the basis of expeditionary methods, maps of the landscape structure of garden and park landscapes of the study area were constructed. Spatial structure models are built in the Corel Draw program based on the digitized surface of the planet Earth in the Google Earth program, vertical profiles of the relief of garden and park landscapes are made with the help of Google Earth Pro tools.

The studies of garden and park landscapes of Central Europe showed that these anthropogenic landscape complexes consist of a set of natural and anthropogenic elements that determine their configuration, shape and physiognomy, as well as a mosaic structure that is constantly changing under the influence of external factors (the predominant factor of transformation is a man), as well as the rhythms and cycles of the functioning of the Earth's landscape envelope.

It should be noted that the dictionary of foreign words gives the following etymology and interpretation of the word «structure» – it is the word of Latin origin (structura – construction, placement); it is the internal structure of something, a certain relationship of the constituent parts of the whole (Melnychuk, 1977). In Merriam-Webster's explanatory dictionary, structure is understood as something arranged in a definite pattern of organization; the arrangement of particles or parts in a substance or body; the organization of parts is determined by the general character of the whole (organization of parts as dominated by the general character of the whole); coherent form or organization; the aggregate of elements of an entity in their relationships to each other.

The structure of not only the garden and park landscapes of Central Europe, but actually of different

groups and classes of man-made landscapes is determined by two categories: space and time (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Types of structures of the garden and park landscapes of the Central Europe

According to the principle of natural-anthropogenic coexistence, the spatial structure of garden and park landscapes of the study area is determined by the combination of natural and anthropogenic tracts and types of localities. The anthropogenic spatial structure of the plain garden and park landscapes of the study area is formed by a set of relevant tracts, which are united within channel, floodplain, slope, supraflood-terrace and watershed types of terrain. These elements of the landscape structure have varying degrees of anthropogenic transformation. It is worth noting that the lowest hypsometric levels of the surface undergo significant changes: these are channel and floodplain types of terrain. During the organization of garden and park landscapes of Central Europe, natural tracts of river-type areas are rebuilt: cascades of ponds are created, breakwaters, swimming pools, canals, waterfalls are built, complex landscape and technical systems of dams and locks are organized, islands are filled. As a result, we have an anthropogenic increase in the area of the water table within the relevant territories (the ratio of active surfaces changes), the transformation of the landscape structure of the stream, changes in the shape and size of floodplain areas, etc. When organizing garden and park landscapes within the boundaries of the Dniester-Dnieper forest-steppe region, the West-Ukrainian region of the broad-leaved forest zone of Ukraine, tracts of slope-type terrain are terraced (for example, the terrace of Muses, the terrace of Belle Vue (the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National

Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, the city of Uman, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine). Palace and park complexes are being built within the tracts of the watershed types of localities (the garden and park landscape of Pechersky Park (Pechera village, Tulchyn district, Vinnytsia Oblast, Ukraine), garden and park landscape «Khoroshe» (Tulchyn, Vinnytsia Oblast, Ukraine), garden and park landscape of Sinytskyi Park (Synytsia Village, Umansky District, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine), Milovidovy Garden and Park Landscape (Potaptsi village, Cherkasy District, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine).

The physiognomy of garden and park landscapes of the study area as an important feature of the spatial organization of anthropogenic landscape complexes is determined by the geological and geomorphological structure of the territory. It is not constant. Its development and changes take place quite quickly and dynamically. The factor that initiates and directs them is a man. The shape and dimensions of garden and park landscapes are determined in accordance with the organization plan of the research objects. Borders are artificial. The area can increase or decrease. As a result, the pattern of garden and park landscapes is very diverse. The internal configuration, the direction of lowering of the physical surface, the general nature of the extension of the object are determined by the river valleys. At the current stage of development, the vast majority of garden and park landscapes in Central Europe are «clamped» by the other types of man-made landscapes, mainly low-rise and agricultural types of residential landscapes.

Fig. 2. Modern spatial configuration of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

The spatio-temporal transformation of the configuration and spatial structure of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine is shown in Figures 3–6.

Fig. 3. The configuration of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine at the beginning of the 19th century

Fig. 4. The configuration of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine at the end of the 1980s

Fig. 5. Configuration of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (1996)

Fig. 6. Modern configuration of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

For example, today the spatial configuration of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine resembles the silhouette of a walking man, the main lines of which are defined by the valley of the Kamyanka River and its tributaries (Fig. 2). In the upper part, it is a triangle that narrows in the direction of the flow of the Kamyanka River, in the south, the garden and park landscape

stretches in a narrow strip within the channel and floodplain types of areas, bordering with low-rise and high-rise types of residential landscapes of the city of Uman, Cherkasy Oblast.

The spatial structure of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiivka» of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine is determined by the direction of the Kamyanka River valley (the South Bug River basin)

and two complex tracts: Zvyrynets and Grekova Balka. The valley of the Kamyanka River stretches from the northeast to the southwest, and from the Nizhniy Pond, which cuts the outcrops of the Ukrainian Crystalline Shield, it changes direction from north to south. Tracts of beams stretched from the west, north-west to the south and south-east. The height difference between watershed and channel tracts of terrain types is 30–40 m; between tracts of the watershed type of areas at the bottom of the streams 20–35 m.

The basis of the spatial structure of the garden and park landscape «Olexandria» (Bila Tserkva, Kyiv Oblast, Ukraine) is formed by a southern exposure slope

inclined to the bed of the Ros river (the Dnipro river basin), cut into four parts by three deep beams. These complex tracts gradually expand towards the river, complicated by tracts of ponds with a total area of about 12 hectares. The spatial configuration of the garden and park landscape «Olexandria» (Bila Tserkva, Kyiv Oblast, Ukraine) (Fig. 9) is determined by the direction of the Ros River. The height difference between the tracts of channel and watershed types of terrain is 30–40 m. Beams are cut to a depth of 15–20 m.

Fig. 9. Modern configuration of the garden and park landscape «Olexandria» (Bila Tserkva, Kyiv Oblast, Ukraine)

It should be noted that the spatial configuration of the vast majority of garden and park landscapes in the study area is determined by the direction of the corresponding hydrographic object. The geological and

geomorphological structure of the territory determines the general character of the change of the physical surface and the vertical profile of the relief, which have been shown in Figures 10–13.

Fig. 10. Vertical profile of the relief of the garden and park landscape of Sinytsky Park (Synytsia village, Umansky district, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine)

Fig. 11. Vertical profile of the relief along the line from the northeast to the southwest of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiyivka» of the NAS of Ukraine (Uman, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine)

Fig. 12. Vertical profile of the relief of the garden and park landscape of the National Dendrological Park «Sofiyivka» of the NAS of Ukraine (Uman, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine)

Fig. 13. Vertical profile of the relief of the Pechero-Sokilets garden and park landscape (Pechera village, Tulchyn district, Vinnytsia Oblast; Sokilets village, Vinnytsia district, Vinnytsia Oblast, Ukraine)

Conclusions and offers. Thus, after conducting a study of the structure of garden and park landscapes of Central Europe, it is possible to formulate the following conclusions. The structure of garden and park landscapes is revealed in space and time. The spatial structure of the research objects is determined by the set of elementary landscape complexes at the local level of organization. The physiognomy is determined by the geological and geomorphological structure, vegetation, small architectural forms and palace and park complexes. Configuration – the shape and dimensions of the garden and park landscape and the direction of the river valley.

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